

IOETA: Include-Only Encoded Architecture for Tsetlin Machine with HDL Automation

Rohan Rajesh Kalbag*, Aditya Gudla*, Farhad Merchant, Simranjeet Singh, and Sachin Patkar

Abstract—Hardware deployment of Machine Learning (ML) algorithms involves a trade-off between resource utilization and performance. The Tsetlin Machine (TM) is an energy- and area-efficient ML algorithm that utilizes elementary logical operations, leading to simpler hardware design and resource-efficient computations. In the TM, propositional formulae (Boolean clauses) are constructed to capture patterns in data. The inclusion or exclusion of a literal in a clause is represented by a single bit known as its Include signal. Existing inference accelerators for TM have limited scalability, as memory and compute requirements increase with model size. We propose the Include-Only Compact Encoding (ICE) scheme and Include-Only Encoded Architecture for Tsetlin Machine with HDL Automation (IOETA), an inference accelerator architecture that leverages the sparseness in Include signals by encoding only literals marked for inclusion. The ICE scheme demonstrates up to a 98% reduction in memory usage. The proposed IOETA architecture is implemented for MNIST, CIFAR-2, and FMNIST datasets and uses 42% less memory than other state-of-the-art encoding schemes. It uses 96% fewer LUTs, 99% fewer registers, 97% less Block RAM, and 85.71% less dynamic power than the vanilla TM implementation. Completely automated generation of verified Register Transfer Level (RTL) descriptions of TM inference architectures allows for their rapid performance benchmarking. For this, we also propose an automated RTL generation framework for TMs that entirely automates the TM hardware implementation flow from training the model to RTL generation to its verification.

Index Terms—Artificial Intelligence, Field Programmable Gate Array, Hardware Acceleration, Tsetlin Machine

I. Introduction

THE usage of Artificial Intelligence (AI)-enabled devices such as smartphones, fitness trackers, medical devices [1], smart drones [2], etc. has become increasingly frequent in the recent past [3] and the AI platform market is expected to grow by nearly 5.4% every year [3]. On-device AI systems require specialized hardware capable of real-time processing with extremely low power and area consumption. Conventionally, deep Artificial Neural Network (ANN) architectures have been utilized for machine learning problems. ANNs rely on complex arithmetic operations, demanding substantial hardware computational resources and memory bandwidth [4]. Active research is focused on enhancing the on-device performance of ANNs

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Fig. 1. Multi-Class Tsetlin Machine architecture having k classes and N clauses per class. Each class has $N/2$ positive and $N/2$ negative clauses indicating votes in favor of or against its own class. The argmax block returns the predicted class with the highest number of votes.

through methods such as compression and quantization, albeit often at the expense of accuracy deterioration [5]. In the realm of quantized neural networks, the Binary Neural Network (BNN) [6] stands out as a popular inference architecture, and FINN by Xilinx Research Labs [7] is a framework for implementing BNNs. The interpretability of an ANN's weights and biases is often limited, leading to ANNs being treated as black boxes [8]. This restricts their use in applications demanding interpretable decision-making, highlighting the necessity for more interpretable ML algorithms [9].

The Tsetlin Machine (TM) is an interpretable ML algorithm that introduces a learning mechanism based on learning automata, called the Tsetlin Automata (TA), offering a more foundational and adaptable approach to learning [10]. The TM operates with Booleanized inputs, necessitating the transformation of the original input into Boolean literals and their corresponding logical complements. The fundamental unit of this architecture comprises clauses representing propositional formulae (Boolean clauses) formed by a conjunction of some or all of these literals. The patterns captured by TMs are propositional formulae easily interpretable by humans, facilitating explainable pattern recognition [11]. In the TM, the learning process involves a supervised feedback-based mechanism to determine which literals to incorporate into a particular clause, and these included literals are indicated by corresponding Include signals. Since the TM's basic blocks consist of logical operations, they can be easily

Fig. 2. Visualization of clause computation for $2n$ -bit-sized one-hot-encoded Include signals. The output of TAs indicates which literal to include for clause computation.

realized on hardware using computationally inexpensive and energy-frugal digital logic. It does not require any complex blocks for floating-point arithmetic, as in the case of ANNs. However, the memory requirements for storing the Include signals, which determine the literals to include in the corresponding clause of the TM architecture, are notably substantial [12].

The Multi-Class Tsetlin Machine (MCTM) is a configuration of the TM used for supervised multi-class classification problems. For each of the k classes, there are N clauses per class, each capturing a propositional formula that either votes in favor of (positive clause) or against (negative clause) its corresponding class. This is followed by an argmax block, which returns the predicted class as the one with the highest number of votes (see Fig. 1). During the computation of a single clause (see Fig. 2), the output of TAs indicates which corresponding literals take part in the clause output generation. The One-Hot Encoding (OHE) scheme discussed for the Noisy XOR dataset in [10], utilizing $2n$ -sized bit vectors, where n denotes the number of Boolean input features in the input data, proves to be highly inefficient for representing the Include signals. Work has been conducted to enhance memory utilization by introducing encoding schemes that solely consider the literals marked for inclusion in the clause [13], [14]. However, these schemes do not optimize the encoding efficiently and can be further compressed, emphasizing the necessity for a more compact representation of the Include signals. Additionally, these encoding schemes utilize a fixed number of bits. They are not

generalizable to MCTMs accepting inputs with arbitrary feature sizes, indicating the need for an encoding method that generalizes to all MCTMs. This paper introduces the Include-Only Compact Encoding (ICE) scheme. This encoding scheme efficiently reduces the number of bits for storing the Include signals, resulting in a resource-, memory-, and power-efficient hardware implementation of the MCTM. Furthermore, it generalizes the encoding to accommodate arbitrary input feature sizes (n), number of classes (k), and number of clauses per class (N), thereby enabling the extension of this encoding to any MCTM implementation.

Moreover, hardware accelerators provide high performance, flexibility, and economical resource utilization. There are various methods to implement accelerators in hardware, such as Hardware Description Language (HDL), High-Level Synthesis-based design, and domain-specific language-based design. It has been shown that HDL-based design is essential for optimizing on-device AI performance [15]. To analyze the performance metrics of any accelerator architecture, such as test accuracy and resource utilization as a function of various hyperparameters, frequent off-system training of models, HDL generation, and verification of the generated HDL are necessary. MATADOR [16] is an automation framework that utilizes open-source Xilinx IPs and hierarchical block design to generate TM RTL. However, there are no HDL generation and verification automation frameworks in the literature for custom HDL-based TM accelerator architectures. To address this, the paper also introduces Automated RTL generation for Tsetlin Machine (ART). This framework takes generalized and parameterized HDL-design templates of the MCTM inference accelerator and runtime values of architectural hyperparameters as input. It conducts off-system training to generate clauses, which are then used to produce runtime-specific synthesizable HDL describing the RTL. Additionally, it generates a testbench containing auto-generated test inputs for the verification of the generated HDL.

This paper proposes Include-Only Encoded Architecture for Tsetlin Machine with HDL Automation (IOETA), a novel resource-efficient, three-stage pipelined architecture for the MCTM. It implements the ICE scheme and utilizes the ART framework for HDL automation. IOETA is implemented for three widely used image classification datasets: MNIST, FMNIST, and CIFAR-2. The variation of the architecture's performance parameters is studied by conducting parameter sweeps and using ART to automate HDL generation for each of these experiments. The generated HDL for MNIST is then synthesized on a Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC ZCU104 FPGA board to study resource utilization and compare it with state-of-the-art MCTM accelerator implementations. In this paper, we highlight the following contributions:

- ICE scheme for memory frugal representation of included literals,
- IOETA architecture, a highly efficient implementation of the ICE scheme, and its comparison with other

Fig. 3. MCTM OHE architecture with one-hot-encoded Include signals stored in k ROMs of size $N \times 2n$.

MCTM accelerator implementations and

- ART framework enabling automated HDL generation and verification for custom HDL-based TM accelerators.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section II gives an overview of TM and related work, Section III discusses the ICE scheme and IOETA architecture, Section IV discusses the ART framework, and Section V presents the methodology and results. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

II. Background and Related Work

A. Tsetlin Machine

The TM used for the multi-class classification pattern recognition task comprises the following submodules:

1) Tsetlin Automata: The TA is a finite state machine having $2M$ hierarchical states. It takes the action α_1 if its current state is from 1 to M , and it takes the action α_2 from $M + 1$ to $2M$. The current state is updated using game-theoretic reinforcement via rewards for true positives and penalties for false positives and false negatives during the learning phase [10]. The reinforcement is dependent on two user-defined hyperparameters, s and T . The hyperparameter s represents stochasticity and the reward probabilities for the learning feedback as a function of stochasticity. T represents the thresholding margin that allows for the distribution of clauses among the various sub-patterns of the provided data [10]. For each clause C_j with n positive literals, there is a team of $2n$ TAs (n for the literals and n for their logical complements). Each TA, depending on its current state, decides to either include (α_1) or not include (α_2) the literal assigned to it in C_j . A snapshot of all $2n$ α_i 's corresponding to all $k \cdot N$ clauses gives us the Include signals.

2) Booleanization Function: The Tsetlin Machine operates on Boolean data. The raw input data is converted to $\{0, 1\}$ -valued Boolean literals by using an appropriate Booleanization function $f : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \{0, 1\}^m$. For an m -dimensional input X_i , the output $f(X_i)$ consists of m

Boolean literals, which can be represented by an m -sized bit-vector $(x_1, x_2 \dots x_m)$. Thus, the training data will consist of examples of the form $(f(X_i), y_i)$, where y_i is the actual class label. The test data should also be Booleanized, indicating that f should be realizable in hardware during inference. An example of a simple Booleanization function is plain thresholding (see eq. (1)).

$$\begin{aligned} f : \mathbb{R}^n &\rightarrow \{0, 1\}^n, \quad Z \in \mathbb{R} \\ f(x_1, x_2 \dots x_n) &= (y_1, y_2 \dots y_n) \\ y_i &= 1 \iff x_i \geq Z; \quad y_i = 0 \iff x_i < Z \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

3) Clauses and Include Signals: In TMs, the recognized patterns are represented as Boolean conjunctive clauses denoted by C , which consist of the input Boolean literals x_i 's and their complements $\neg x_i$'s. If there are n positive literals, the bits of a $\{0, 1\}^{2n}$ bit-vector represent whether to include their corresponding literal in the clause or not. These one-hot-encoded bit-vectors are called the Include signals for the corresponding clause. For example, if we have a clause $C(x_0, x_1, \neg x_0, \neg x_1) = x_0 \wedge \neg x_1$, we can uniquely represent this clause using 4 Include signals $\{1, 0, 0, 1\}$ for $\{x_0, x_1, \neg x_0, \neg x_1\}$. These Include signals that hold the learned information are analogous to weights in ANNs. They are generated off-system during training and represent whether to include or exclude a particular Boolean literal x_i in the clause C_j . The number of clauses per class (N) in the TM is a user-defined hyperparameter. For an MCTM architecture with N clauses per class, k classes, and n input literals, there will be $2n \cdot k \cdot N$ Include signals.

4) Voting and Argmax: If the number of clauses per class (N) is fixed, then $N/2$ of these are positive clauses (denoted by C_j^+) and the remaining $N/2$ are negative clauses (denoted by C_j^-). For an MCTM with k classes, each class will have a voting module that assigns a weight of $+1$ to each positive clause and a weight of -1 to each negative clause. The output of the voting module for the m^{th} class is expressed in eq. (2).

$$v_m = \sum_{j=0}^{N/2-1} (C_j^+ \cdot (+1)) + \sum_{j=0}^{N/2-1} (C_j^- \cdot (-1)) \quad (2)$$

The v_m outputs corresponding to each class label $0 \leq m \leq (k-1)$ are fed to an argmax module, which returns the index m corresponding to the largest v_m (eq. (3))

$$y_{\text{pred}} = \text{argmax}_{m \in 0 \dots k-1} (v_m) \quad (3)$$

The class that has the highest number of votes is considered to be the predicted output of the MCTM. For example, if we had three classes k_0, k_1, k_2 with $v_0, v_1, v_2 = \{2, 5, 3\}$, then y_{pred} would be v_1 .

5) MCTM Architecture for OHE Include Signals: In the architecture used to implement a MCTM having k classes with N clauses each (see Fig. 3), the OHE Include signals require k ROMs of size $N \times 2n$ for storage. At every clock cycle, Include signals of the clauses are read from the corresponding ROMs and given as inputs to the

clause compute modules. Each clause compute module has two inputs, viz. $2n$ -bit input literals and $2n$ -bit Include signals, and a single 1-bit output. To generate all clause outputs, N clock cycles are required, and each clause output is stored in its corresponding register. After all the clause outputs are generated, k voting modules perform polarity assignment and summation of the clause outputs (Section II-A4) in $N/2$ clock cycles. The total number of clock cycles required by this architecture for making the final prediction is $N + N/2$.

B. Related Work

The MCTM OHE architecture, first proposed in [10], uses a total of $2n \cdot k \cdot N$ memory bits to store all OHE Include signals. The memory requirement increases with n , k , and N . This means that memory scales with the size of the TM model to be implemented, thereby limiting scalability. It is observed that there is a high level of sparsity in the OHE Include signals. For example, in an MCTM with 400 clauses and hyperparameters $s = 10$, $T = 20$ trained for 25 epochs on the MNIST dataset (10 classes), out of the 6,272,000 OHE bits ($400 \times 10 \times 784 \times 2$), only 125,941 bits (approximately 2%) are set to one and correspond to included literals, while the rest consist of zeroes.

REDRESS [13] introduced the Include-Encoding scheme, which partially alleviates the sparsity problem by storing only information related to included literals. It utilizes 16-bit integer words, comprising a 14-bit literal offset and 2-bit additional information for each included literal. Additionally, it includes a data structure with 16-bit integer words containing the number of included literals for each class. While this scheme notably reduces the memory footprint compared to the OHE implementation, it is limited to MCTMs with input literals restricted to 14 bits ($\lceil \log_2(2n) \rceil \leq 14$, where $\lceil \cdot \rceil$ denotes the ceiling function) for their representation and does not discuss generalization to any input feature size. This scheme is designed for embedded MCTM implementations and necessitates words to be multiples of 16 bits to be stored in memory, constrained by the architecture of the microcontroller used. This prevents the scheme from achieving optimal compactness, particularly in the context of FPGAs and Application Specific Integrated Circuits (ASICs), where memory width adjustments can allow the accommodation of words with arbitrary size.

Sahu et al. [14] introduced an alternative encoding scheme for MCTMs utilizing Block RAMs for memory in FPGAs. This scheme employs 32-bit words, comprising 24 bits of information about the included literal, its class and clause, and the remaining 8 bits consisting of 8 test image literals for each included literal. However, this scheme does not optimally encode information, and the number of bits can be further reduced from 24 bits without any loss. Additionally, this scheme is specific to MCTMs trained on the MNIST dataset and does not address generalization for an arbitrary number of input features.

Fig. 4. Include-only Compact Encoding (ICE) scheme. clu = clause change bit, pol = clause polarity bit, cla = class change bit, $litaddr$ = index of included literal

MATADOR [16] uses open-source Xilinx IPs for the heterogeneous SoC-FPGA-based design of TM accelerators. IOETA is a purely FPGA-based architecture, unlike MATADOR, and due to the difference in their implementation methodologies, a direct fair comparison is not possible between these architectures.

III. ICE and IOETA

A. The ICE Scheme

In the MCTM OHE architecture, as the size of ROM increases, its decoder size also increases, thereby utilizing many resources and much power. Implementation of such an architecture on resource-constrained hardware is not possible for large TM models due to limited resources, especially memory. It becomes necessary to decrease memory utilization by using an alternative encoding scheme. We introduce the ICE scheme, which enables a more efficient implementation of the TM on resource-constrained hardware. The ICE scheme (see Fig. 4) exploits the sparsity of Include signals and encodes only the literals marked for inclusion by the TAs. For each included literal, an encoded word of size W bits (computed in eq. (4)) is generated. The encoded word consists of 1 bit for Clause Change, 1 bit for Clause Polarity, 1 bit for Class Change, and $\lceil \log_2(2n) \rceil$ bits for the Literal Address, where $\lceil \cdot \rceil$ denotes the ceiling function.

$$W = 3 + \lceil \log_2(2n) \rceil \quad (4)$$

For instance, in MNIST 28×28 image classification, each included literal is encoded using $W_{MNIST} = 3 + \lceil \log_2(28 \times 28 \times 2) \rceil = 14$ -bit words.

The bits of the encoded-word have the following meaning:

1) Clause Change (*clu*): A toggling of this bit signifies that the current encoded word is associated with a new clause of the same class. It also indicates the completion of processing for all the encoded words corresponding to the included literals in the preceding clause.

2) Clause Polarity (*pol*): It signifies whether the current encoded word corresponds to a clause with positive or negative polarity. A value of 0 denotes a positive clause, while a value of 1 represents a negative clause.

3) Class Change (*cla*): A toggling of this bit signifies that the current encoded word is associated with a new clause of the next class. It also signals the completion of processing for all the clauses associated with the current class and prompts the decoding logic to transition to the next class.

4) Literal Address (*litaddr*): These bits encode a number i , representing the index of the literal to be included. They indicate that the current encoded word corresponds to the i^{th} literal included in the current clause, where i ranges from 0 to $(2n - 1)$. For example, in the context of MNIST, if the current word has a literal address of i , it implies including the i^{th} literal from the set $\{x_{783}, x_{782}, \dots, x_0, \neg x_{783}, \dots, \neg x_0\}$ in the computation of the current clause output.

B. Encoding Transformation

To convert the $2n$ -bit OHE Include signals to the ICE scheme, Algorithm 1 is employed. In this algorithm, \circ denotes the string concatenation operation, ‘x’ denotes “don’t care” bits that can be either 0 or 1, and the Bits (x, y) method takes a number x and returns its binary representation of y bits. For example, Bits (10, 4) would yield “1010”. In cases where the clauses do not contain any literals, i.e., the OHE Include signals for the clause correspond to “000...0”, an encoded word is added with an invalid clause address p from the set $P = \{2n, 2n + 1, \dots, 2^{\lceil \log_2(2n) \rceil} - 1\}$ to inform the decoding logic. This encoding transformation generates $I W$ -bit ICE-encoded words from $k \cdot N$ OHE Include signals.

C. IOETA Architecture

The architecture that uses the ICE encoding scheme consists of a ROM, clause computation module (see Fig. 5a), voting and argmax module (see Fig. 5b), and class update module (see Fig. 5c). A ROM of size $I \times W$ is used to store the encoded Include signals of $N \times k$ clauses. At every clock cycle, an encoded word is read from the ROM, decoded, and given as input to the respective modules. The clause output (c) is updated at every clock cycle as follows (see Fig. 5a): $clu = prev(clu)$ indicates that the current encoded literal is also part of the clause; thus, $c \leftarrow c \& x_{litaddr}$ (\leftarrow operation denotes updating). Conversely, $clu \neq prev(clu)$ indicates that the current encoded literal is part of the next clause; c is employed for voting and subsequently set to $c \leftarrow 1 \& x_{litaddr}$ to initiate computation for the next clause. The class number (d) represents the class for which the current clause votes. It is

updated at every clock cycle as follows: if $cla \neq prev(cla)$, indicating the start of the next class, d is incremented by 1 ($d \leftarrow d+1$) (see Fig. 5c); otherwise, it remains unchanged. Next, d selects the vote register for its corresponding class from the register file. The register is updated depending on the values of c and pol : if $pol = 0$, then $v_d \leftarrow v_d + c$; otherwise, $v_d \leftarrow v_d - c$ (see Fig. 5b).

The IOETA architecture has a three-stage pipeline. The stages of the implemented pipeline are fetch, clause compute, and voting. In the fetch stage, the output of the ROM is read; in the next stage, the clause output is calculated; and in the last stage, the voting value is generated. The number of fetch cycles would be equal to the depth of the ROM, i.e., I , and after fetching the last encoded word, two additional clock cycles are needed to generate the last voting value. After all the voting values are generated, the final prediction is made based on the output from the argmax module. The total number of clock cycles required to make the final prediction is $I + 2$, indicating that clock cycles are dependent on the number of Include signals generated during training.

IV. ART Framework

The ART framework enables the generation of runtime-specific synthesizable RTL for custom HDL-based TM ac-

Algorithm 1 Convert OHE Include signals to ICE scheme

Input: OneHotEncodedSignals (list of $2n$ -bit vectors)
Output: CompactSignals (list of W -bit vectors)

- 1: Initialize an empty array CompactSignals
- 2: Initialize classchange $\leftarrow 0$; clausechange $\leftarrow 0$
- 3: for class $\leftarrow 0$ to $k - 1$ do
- 4: for clause $\leftarrow 0$ to $N - 1$ do
- 5: $wt \leftarrow \text{OneHotEncodedSignals}[\text{class}][\text{clause}]$
- 6: if wt is “000...0” then
- 7: $wt_{enc} \leftarrow \text{“xxx”} \circ \text{Bits}(p, \lceil \log_2(2n) \rceil)$
- 8: Append wt_{enc} to CompactSignals
- 9: else
- 10: for $i \leftarrow 0$ to $2n - 1$ do
- 11: if i^{th} bit of wt is 1 then
- 12: $wt_{enc} \leftarrow wt_{enc} \circ \text{clausechange}$ (1 bit)
- 13: if $i < N/2$ (positive clause) then
- 14: $wt_{enc} \leftarrow wt_{enc} \circ 0$ (1 bit clause polarity)
- 15: else
- 16: $wt_{enc} \leftarrow wt_{enc} \circ 1$ (1 bit clause polarity)
- 17: end if
- 18: $wt_{enc} \leftarrow \text{classchange}$ (1 bit)
- 19: literaladdress = Bits($i, \lceil \log_2(2n) \rceil$)
- 20: $wt_{enc} \leftarrow wt_{enc} \circ \text{literaladdress}$
- 21: Append wt_{enc} to CompactSignals
- 22: end if
- 23: end for
- 24: clausechange $\leftarrow \neg \text{clausechange}$
- 25: end if
- 26: end for
- 27: classchange $\leftarrow \neg \text{classchange}$
- 28: end for

Fig. 5. IOETA Architecture. (a) Shows generation of clause output depending on current and previous clause change bits (*clu*) and the input literal corresponding to the literal address (*litaddr*). (b) Shows addition/subtraction of clause output from the voting value depending on the polarity bit (*pol*) and class number (*d*). (c) Shows updating of class number (*d*) based on current and previous class change bits (*cla*).

celerator architectures. This framework entirely automates the TM hardware implementation flow from training the model to RTL generation to its verification using auto-generated test inputs. Various components of this framework are explained in the subsequent subsections.

A. Requirements

ART has the following prerequisites that must be met to enable the automation of RTL for a custom HDL-based TM accelerator design:

Listing 1

Example of parameterization in Scalable HDL Templates using the parameter construct of Verilog

```

module Voting #(parameter NUM_CLASSES = 10)(
  input [NUM_CLASSES/2-1 : 0] pos, neg,
  output [31:0] vote
);
  ...
endmodule

```

Listing 2

Example of hierarchical design in Scalable HDL Templates using the generic construct of Verilog

```

module MultiClassTM(
  input [WIDTH-1:0] img,
  output [3:0] pred
);
  reg [2*WORD_SIZE-1:0] includes [0:NUM_WORDS-1]
  $readmemb(WEIGHT_FILE, includes);

  wire [NUM_CLAUSES/2-1] pos [0:NUM_CLASSES-1];
  wire [NUM_CLAUSES/2-1] neg [0:NUM_CLASSES-1];
  wire [31:0] votes [0:NUM_CLASSES-1];
  ...
  genvar i;
  generate // systematic instantiation starts here
  for (i=0; i<NUM_CLASSES-1; i=i+1) begin
    Voting v #(NUM_CLAUSES)(
      .pos(pos[i]),
      .neg(neg[i]),
      .vote(votes[i])
    );
  end
  endgenerate // systematic instantiation ends
  ...
endmodule

```

1) Scalable HDL Templates: To automate RTL generation using ART, the user must create the submodules of the HDL-based accelerator as Scalable HDL Templates (SHTs) keeping the following in mind:

The templates should be parameterized, utilizing machine-synthesizable constructs such as *parameter* in Verilog HDL and *generic* in VHDL. An example of this is the usage of *NUM_CLAUSES* as a parameter for the *Voting* Verilog module (see Listing 1). This enables ART to adapt the same architecture template for different configurations and port sizes.

The templates should adopt a hierarchical design approach, wherein submodules are instantiated using HDL constructs such as *generate* in Verilog HDL and *for-generate* in VHDL. This ensures a systematic and organized instantiation of submodules, allowing for indexing and facilitating streamlined automated code generation by ART. For instance, the SHT for the *Voting* module (see Listing 1) is systematically instantiated within the SHT for the Verilog module *MultiClassTM* using the *generate* construct, as illustrated by the lower highlighted snippet (in red) in Listing 2. The SHTs can be adapted for various HDLs such as VHDL, Verilog, SystemVerilog, and others. This flexibility allows ART to produce RTL code specific to the chosen HDL, depending on the targeted backend device or EDA toolchain.

2) Off-System Training API: For ART to perform training and generate clause Include signals on demand depending on runtime architectural hyperparameters or freshly obtained data in the case of online learning, it must have access to a software implementation of the training API. For IOETA, the training is performed using the *TMClassifier* API of the Tsetlin Machine Unified (TMU) Python library developed by CAIR [17]. The API takes architectural hyperparameters as input: number of literals (*n*), number of clauses per class (*N*), number of classes

(k), thresholding margin (T), stochasticity s , and number of epochs N_E . After training an instance of the model with all the architectural parameters for N_E epochs, ART identifies which literals are present in a particular clause using the *TMClassifier* API’s *get_ta_action()* method, which gives information on whether the TA included the corresponding literal or not. These are then used to create the $\{0, 1\}^{2n}$ one-hot-encoded Include signals w_i ’s corresponding to each clause. These $N \cdot k$ one-hot-encoded vectors are then stored in a file with a naming convention consisting of the architectural hyperparameters.

B. Implementation

This subsection delves into the internal workings of ART. ART consists of the following components:

1) Automation Supervisor Program: The Automation Supervisor Program receives runtime hyperparameters and SHTs from the user. It then processes the inputs and generates hyperparameter-specific RTL. This program consists of the following submodules:

Command Line Interface (CLI): This provides an efficient means for the user to input the runtime hyperparameters. The CLI should also allow the program to receive the relative or absolute path of the files containing the SHTs. Having a CLI not only simplifies the validation of program inputs but also enables remote users to SSH into servers with computational resources, thereby facilitating the execution of numerous tasks and instances of the automation framework through shell scripting. Through the CLI, the program obtains runtime hyperparameters, SHTs, and additional configurations from the user.

HDL Template Preprocessor: The program reads the SHTs $T_1, T_2 \dots T_n$ from their respective files, obtains the set of runtime hyperparameters $S = S_1 \cup S_2 \cup \dots S_n$ from the CLI, replaces the parameter constants (*generics, parameters*) in T_i with their runtime values in S_i , and returns the runtime-specific RTL templates T'_i . An algorithm that does the same can be seen in Algorithm 2. ART implements this by inserting format specifiers such as “%s” in place of the constant whenever there is a parameter instantiation in Verilog or generic map in VHDL while reading the T_i multiline strings. The placeholders can then be easily replaced by their respective runtime hyperparameters through simple string manipulation.

Algorithm 2 Preprocess and Replace Parameter Constants

Input: Scalable HDL Template Filenames F_1, F_2, \dots, F_n ;

Runtime Hyperparameter Set $S = S_1 \cup S_2 \cup \dots \cup S_n$

Output: Runtime-Specific SHTs $T'_1, T'_2 \dots T'_n$

- 1: for $i \leftarrow 1$ to n do
 - 2: $T_i \leftarrow \text{ReadTemplateFromFile}(F_i)$
 - 3: for each parameter p in T_i and s in S_i do
 - 4: $\text{ReplaceConstantWithRuntimeValue}(p, s)$
 - 5: end for
 - 6: $T'_i \leftarrow \text{SaveModifiedTemplate}(T_i)$
 - 7: end for
-

Model Weight Processor: The program utilizes the Off-System Training API (TMU [17]) discussed earlier. It provides the API with runtime architectural hyperparameters, performs the training, and generates a file consisting of $2n$ -sized bit-vectors $w_i \in \{0, 1\}^{2n}$. Within the file, the bit-vectors corresponding to each clause are stacked on $k \cdot N$ new lines. The program implements an encoding transformation function f_E that takes these sparse OHE Include signals and returns a filename for the generated compact encoded Include signals. In the case of IOETA, the program implements the transform for ICE (Algorithm 1). Subsequently, the program identifies the storage M (as a *register* in Verilog or a *signal* in VHDL) within the runtime-specific SHT T'_k , which will synthesize to Block RAM representing the clause Include signals utilized by the accelerator for inference. An example of such a storage signal can be observed in the upper highlighted snippet (in orange) of Listing 2. The program then maps the compact encoded weight file to the storage. An algorithm that accomplishes this is shown in Algorithm 3. The initialization of the storage is executed as follows: In certain HDLs, it is feasible to initialize register signals in a hardware-synthesizable manner directly from a file. For instance, ART accomplishes this in Verilog using the $\$readmemb(filename, M)$ syntax (see Listing 2). Here, the encoded words from the *CompactSignals* array in Algorithm 3 can be stored line by line in a separate file with the specified *filename*, situated in the same directory. If the HDL does not allow for initialization from a file, then RTL code for weight mapping can be easily generated by iterating through *CompactSignals* and employing string manipulation techniques.

File Management: After generating the runtime-specific RTL initialized with encoded Include signals T''_i , the program saves the generated RTL to files for subsequent usage by other EDA tools. The CLI accepts a configuration parameter that allows either overwriting the files, which is suitable for resource-constrained applications, or storing the RTL in new files using a naming convention consisting of runtime hyperparameters. This is particularly useful for applications where results need to be tracked for research experimentation, such as parameter sweeps. The latter approach is utilized in the case of IOETA to study its experimental performance parameters.

Algorithm 3 Encoding Transformation and Map To RTL

Input: Storage signal M from Weight Template RTL T'_k ;

File with One-Hot-Encoded Include signals F_W

Output: RTL for Encoded Include signals T''_k

- 1: Initialize an empty array *CompactSignals*
 - 2: for $i \leftarrow 1$ to $\text{TotalLinesIn}(F_W)$ do
 - 3: $w_i \leftarrow \text{ReadLineFromFile}(F_W)$
 - 4: $w'_i \leftarrow \text{PerformTransformation}(w_i)$
 - 5: Append w'_i to *CompactSignals*
 - 6: end for
 - 7: $T''_k \leftarrow \{T'_k - M\} \cup \text{InitMemory}(\text{CompactSignals}, M)$
-

2) Verification Program: An extremely crucial aspect of any automated framework is verification; this ensures that the generated RTL code is correct, eliminating the need for subsequent steps in the design flow to independently check for correctness. Ensuring the reliability and accuracy of RTL code is paramount, especially in the context of inference accelerators, where the accuracy should match that of its pure software implementation to demonstrate equivalence. Therefore, ART incorporates a verification program that takes the RTL generated by the Automation Supervisor Program and produces appropriate test vectors corresponding to test data examples from the dataset. These vectors are then applied to the generated RTL, its behavior is simulated in software, its output is asserted, and accuracy is benchmarked. This process involves comparing the output with the software implementation present in the Off-System Training API. The verification program comprises the following subparts:

Testbench Generator: This component of the program is responsible for generating the RTL for a testbench that instantiates the top-level module (TLM) of the generated RTL. The program selects examples (X_i, y_i) from the dataset utilized in the Off-System Training API employed for weight generation and stores these pairs in a storage variable within the RTL, accomplished through string manipulation techniques. Additionally, the testbench includes a sequential procedural block that takes each X_i , applies it to the TLM, waits for the desired number of clock cycles, allows the accelerator to settle, and then samples the output y_{pred} . The block then verifies whether y_{pred} is equal to y_i and keeps track of the accuracy.

Simulation Framework: HDL-specific simulation frameworks with a command-line interface are utilized for simulating the generated testbench. ART employs Icarus Verilog [18] for Verilog and ghdl [19] for VHDL. The accuracy benchmarked by the testbench is logged to the console, allowing the user to quantify the reliability of the generated RTL.

The ART framework is used to conduct several experiments and generate results, which are presented next in Section V. The hardware implementation results are also presented in Section V; they are generated in Vivado using verified RTLs created by the ART framework.

V. Implementation and Results

This section discusses various implementation methodologies and experimental results in detail.

A. Dataset Selection and Preprocessing

To compare the performance and resource utilization of the proposed framework with other comparable implementations, experiments were conducted on the following datasets: MNIST (comprising 28×28 input images of handwritten digits with 10 possible labels), FMNIST (comprising 28×28 input images of fashion items with 10 possible labels), and CIFAR-2 (a variation of the CIFAR-10 dataset consisting of 32×32 input images with

2 possible labels). To Booleanize the inputs, adaptive Gaussian thresholding is employed with a window size of 11 and a threshold value of 2 for MNIST, FMNIST, and CIFAR-2, as suggested in [13].

B. Automation Using ART

The scalable Verilog HDL templates describing the architecture’s submodules are fed into ART. A script is used to specify the architectural hyperparameters for conducting sweeps. The script then invokes ART and provides these hyperparameters to its CLI one by one.

ART then conducts training, generates the RTL and testbench for each experiment, runs the simulation, and logs the accuracy (on the test data in %), the number of includes (I), the percentage of includes (PI) computed using eq. (5), and the percentage reduction (PR) in the number of memory bits compared to OHE, computed using eq. (6).

$$PI = \frac{I}{N \cdot k \cdot 2n} \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

$$PR = \frac{N \cdot k \cdot 2n - I \cdot W}{N \cdot k \cdot 2n} \cdot 100 \quad (6)$$

The RTL for OHE MCTM architecture implementation with the same runtime hyperparameters is also generated to facilitate a fair comparison of resource utilization.

C. Conducting Parameter Sweeps

To investigate the variation of accuracy, I , PI , and PR with various hyperparameters, sweeps of each hyperparameter are conducted while keeping others constant. The hyperparameters are initialized at random to (N_0, T_0, s_0) . The initial sweep involved varying the number of clauses and identifying the point corresponding to the highest accuracy. Once the optimal number of clauses is determined, it is fixed, and a subsequent sweep is performed for the parameter T until the point corresponding to the highest accuracy is found. Following this, T is also fixed, and a final sweep is conducted for the parameter s to identify the 3-tuple $(N_{max}, T_{max}, s_{max})$ corresponding to the maximum accuracy. The dataset-specific experiments and their results were as follows:

In each experiment, the training is performed for 25 epochs, 10 epochs, and 5 epochs in the case of MNIST, FMNIST, and CIFAR-2, respectively. The hyperparameters are initialized as (100, 20, 10) for MNIST, (200, 50, 10) for FMNIST, and (200, 50, 10) for CIFAR-2. The number of clauses is varied from 100 to 2000, 200 to 9600, and 200 to 9600 for MNIST, FMNIST, and CIFAR-2, respectively. The accuracy is maximized at 800 clauses for MNIST, 4800 clauses for FMNIST, and 3200 clauses for CIFAR-2 (see Fig. 6a). Then, the value of T is varied from 20 to 45 for MNIST, from 20 to 80 for FMNIST, and from 10 to 70 for CIFAR-2. The maximal accuracy was obtained at $T = 35$ for MNIST and at $T = 60$ for FMNIST and CIFAR-2 (see Fig. 6b). Finally, the value of s was varied from 5 to 15 for

MNIST, from 5 to 15 for FMNIST, and from 2.5 to 15 for CIFAR-2. The point corresponding to the highest accuracy was obtained as (800, 35, 10) for MNIST, (4800, 60, 7.5) for FMNIST, and (3200, 60, 5) for CIFAR-2 (see Fig. 6c).

D. Analysis of Parameter Sweeps

By examining the plots presented in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8, we can infer the following points:

1) Effect of number of clauses: PI decreases as N increases (see Fig. 7a). In other words, the sparsity of Include signals increases with an increase in N . For the ICE scheme, PR increases steadily with an increase in N (see Fig. 8a) because of the decrease in PI as N increases. This trend suggests that as the number of clauses increases, the number of bits required to represent the Include signals using the ICE scheme becomes significantly lower than with OHE. This suggests that larger TM models are efficiently implemented using the ICE scheme. However, when N is very small and suboptimal for capturing all the patterns in the data, using the ICE scheme over OHE is disadvantageous because of negative PR (see Fig. 8a for MNIST).

2) Effect of thresholding margin: PI steadily increases with the increase in T (see Fig. 7b). Since PI increases, PR decreases with the increase in T (see Fig. 8b).

3) Effect of stochasticity: PI steadily increases with the increase in s (see Fig. 7c). Since PI increases, PR decreases with the increase in s (see Fig. 8b). For MNIST, PR decreases rapidly as a consequence of the rapid increase in PI .

E. Hardware Results

The RTL generated by ART for MCTM using OHE and IOETA architecture is implemented on the Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC ZCU104 FPGA board using Vivado 2023.1 to generate the experimental results presented in this section. This board has an XCZU7EV-2FFVC1156 device with 230400 CLB LUTs, 460800 CLB Registers, and 11 Mb of total block RAM.

The encoding scheme implemented in [14] uses 24 bits per Include signal. The ICE scheme is an improvement over it, as it uses only 14 bits per Include signal, i.e., it uses 41.67% less memory. In [13], a similar encoding scheme is discussed for storing Include signals. Here, two data arrays are used for inference: a $16 \times k$ array is used to store the number of includes per class, and a $16 \times I$ array is used to store the encoded Include signals. For MNIST, the total number of bits required for the encoding scheme presented in [13] is $160 + 16 \times I$, whereas for ICE it is $14 \times I$. For very small I , say $I = 10$, the reduction in memory utilization for ICE would be 56.25%, and for very large I , the memory reduction for ICE saturates to 12.5%.

Table I shows memory utilization (in KB) for OHE, 24-bit encoding [14], REDRESS [13], and ICE for handwritten digit prediction in MNIST. From this table, it can be concluded that ICE achieves 41.67% lower memory utilization than 24-bit encoding and 12.5% lower utilization than

Fig. 6. Variation of test accuracy with hyperparameters for the parameter sweep experiments conducted. (a) accuracy vs number of clauses (b) accuracy vs hyperparameter T (c) accuracy vs hyperparameter s

REDRESS. It is important to note that for any encoding scheme, memory utilization is enhanced compared to OHE only when PI is below a specific threshold. For ICE to reduce memory usage compared to OHE, the percentage

TABLE I
Memory utilization by OHE, 24-bit encoding [14], REDRESS [13] encoding, and ICE scheme in KB.

Clauses	Includes (%)	OHE	24-bit	REDRESS	ICE
100	16.91	191.41	776.62	517.77	453.03
150	11.97	287.11	824.7	549.82	481.08
200	7.76	382.81	712.84	475.25	415.82
400	2.01	765.63	368.97	246	215.23
800	1.06	1531.25	389.21	259.49	227.04
1200	1.02	2296.88	560.5	373.69	326.96
1600	1.1	3062.5	808.13	538.77	471.41
2000	1.19	3828.13	1093.66	729.13	637.97

Fig. 7. Variation of percentage of includes with hyperparameters for the parameter sweep experiments conducted. (a) percentage of includes vs number of clauses (b) percentage of includes vs hyperparameter T (c) percentage of includes vs hyperparameter s

of includes (PI) must be less than 7.14% (for $W = 14$). For $N = 100, 150$ and 200 , the ICE scheme uses more memory than OHE (still less than the other two encoding schemes) as PI is greater than 7.14% (see highlighted cells in Table I).

As mentioned in Section III-A, the OHE architecture is not implementable on hardware due to the high memory requirement for a large TM model. On the other hand, the IOETA architecture is easily implementable, as it is resource efficient. Table II shows implementation time (in *mins*), BRAM utilization (in %), and dynamic power consumption (in W) for the OHE and IOETA architectures. It can be observed that for the OHE architecture, implementation time and dynamic power consumption increase with the increasing number of clauses, since resource utilization increases with the increasing number of clauses. BRAM utilization for the OHE architecture also

Fig. 8. Variation of percentage reduction of bits with hyperparameters for the parameter sweep experiments conducted. (a) percentage reduction vs number of clauses (b) percentage reduction vs hyperparameter T (c) percentage reduction vs hyperparameter s

increases with an increase in the number of clauses, and for $N = 800, 1200, 1600, 2000$, the OHE architecture is not implementable on the Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC ZCU104 FPGA board since the BRAM requirement is more than 100% (see yellow highlighted cells in Table II). The IOETA architecture, on the other hand, is implemented easily on the target FPGA board. The implementation time and dynamic power consumption are much lower for the IOETA architecture than the OHE architecture, and they also remain approximately the same for all N . The BRAM utilization for the IOETA architecture is significantly lower compared to the OHE architecture when the sparsity of includes is more than 7.14%; as high as an 88% reduction in memory is observed for the IOETA architecture (see green highlighted cell in Table II).

The IOETA architecture becomes more effective compared to the OHE architecture when the sparsity of includes increases. With increasing sparsity of includes

TABLE II
OHE vs IOETA comparison w.r.t. implementation time, BRAM utilization, and dynamic power for the Xilinx Zynq UltraScale+ MPSoC ZCU104 FPGA board.

Clauses	Includes (%)	Accuracy (%)	OHE			IOETA		
			Imp time (min)	BRAM (%)	Dyn Pwr (W)	Imp time (min)	BRAM (%)	Dyn Pwr (W)
100	16.91	88.64	23.75	33.65	0.19	12.85	40.38	0.052
150	11.97	93.39	25.75	35.74	0.205	12.73	40.38	0.053
200	7.76	95.17	33.68	38.3	0.229	12.52	35.9	0.055
400	2.01	96.58	34.67	46.15	0.287	11.65	17.95	0.041
800	1.06	96.82	-	107.85	-	11.87	22.44	0.039
1200	1.02	96.70	-	224.68	-	12.08	26.92	0.044
1600	1.1	96.56	-	235.42	-	12.88	40.38	0.053
2000	1.19	96.45	-	240.06	-	13.37	53.85	0.067

Fig. 9. Experimental results from Vivado's utilization reports. (a) Shows resource utilization of OHE and IOETA architecture (b) Shows reduction in BRAM utilization as sparsity increases.

TABLE III
OHE vs IOETA resource utilization comparison for MNIST, FMNIST, and CIFAR-2 datasets.

Dataset		MNIST	FMNIST	CIFAR-2
Clauses		800	4800	3200
OHE	LUTs (%)	3.6	10.9	3.47
	Registers (%)	2.25	10.6	2.64
	BRAM Util (%)	107.85	976.44	143.4
IOETA	LUTs (%)	0.42 (-76%)	0.48 (-96%)	0.39 (-89%)
	Registers (%)	0.1 (-96%)	0.11 (-99%)	0.22 (-92%)
	BRAM Util (%)	22.44 (-80%)	35.9 (-96%)	4.17 (-97%)

(decreasing PI), the reduction in BRAM utilization increases for IOETA compared to the OHE architecture (see Fig. 9b). The utilization (in %) for different resources such as LUTs, Registers, and BRAM can be observed in Fig. 9a. The IOETA architecture utilizes significantly fewer LUTs

and Registers compared to the OHE architecture (see Fig. 9a). For $N = 100$ & 150, BRAM utilization of the IOETA architecture is slightly more than that of the OHE architecture, but utilization of LUTs and Registers is significantly less. Hence, it is still better to use the IOETA architecture for overall lower resource utilization, even though there might be no reduction in memory. Also, the utilization of LUTs and Registers remains approximately the same in the case of IOETA, but utilization of these resources increases for the OHE architecture with an increasing number of N , highlighting its extreme scalability.

The results presented in Table I, Table II, and Fig. 9 were generated for the implementation of handwritten digit recognition on the MNIST dataset. Table III shows the resource utilization comparison between IOETA and OHE architecture for two more datasets: FMNIST and CIFAR-2. It is evident from this table that the ICE

scheme and IOETA architecture are extremely efficient for hardware implementation. The highest overall reduction of resources is observed for the FMNIST dataset, with a reduction of 96% LUTs, 99% Registers, and 96.32% BRAM (see highlighted cells in Table III).

As mentioned in Section III-C, the number of clock cycles required by the IOETA architecture to generate the final output is $I + 2$, and for the OHE architecture, it is $N + N/2$. Since $I \gg N$, the number of clock cycles required by the IOETA architecture is much greater than that required by the OHE architecture. Hence, there is a trade-off between less resource utilization and more clock cycles. To reduce the number of clock cycles, the number of includes in all the clauses must be reduced during training. In [20], the authors discuss a literal budgeting method that helps reduce the number of includes in each clause significantly while maintaining good accuracy.

VI. Conclusion

The TM is a novel and lightweight ML algorithm that is suitable for resource- and power-constrained computations necessary for inference on edge devices. This paper introduced the IOETA architecture for the MCTM, which is an efficient and scalable inference architecture that employs the ICE scheme. The ICE scheme is a generalized, optimized, and lossless compression methodology that takes advantage of sparseness in the clauses for efficient storage of Include signals in memory. The IOETA architecture outperformed other MCTM implementations utilizing different state-of-the-art encoding schemes in terms of memory utilization, hardware resource utilization, and on-chip power consumption. The comparison results were also presented in this paper for inference across three benchmark datasets: MNIST, CIFAR-2, and FMNIST. Lastly, this paper presented the ART framework, which enables seamless HDL generation and design verification of custom HDL-based TM accelerator architectures. This framework significantly reduces the person-hours required for runtime-specific RTL generation and hardware experimentation in research.

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